

LEOFETs with three polymer based designs.

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Abstract:

The symmetric state transfer-resistance transfer-semantic transfer in a uniform design of state based circuit theory, as a generalization of thin client based computing is inspired by design thinking paradigms like the C+ language, (“Website” n.d.) primarily developed towards ending memory buffer overflow attacks, and in the creation of scalable quantum scale computing. Spin Torque Transfer adds spin wave functionality to adiabatic control theory implementations in circuit theory for reconfigurability. An atomic unit of this paradigm is in waveguide coupled LE-OFETS, the possible future of flexible circuits and a contender for minimalist designs for the quantum e-paper project.

In this paper we use MaC to model mathematically one such atomic design of a LE-OFET.

Keywords: LE-OFET, state transfer, resistance transfer, spin torque transfer, semantic transfer, e-paper, quantum e-paper, flexible circuits,

What:

Design of LE-OFETs for fast switching and infinite input impedance FET designs, for high density integration and quantum scale computing, extendable to single photon computing applications.

In this paper we design waveguide coupled integrated OLED and OFET devices coupled as a single device with a single LDR inspired photosensitive polymer and a single light emitting polymer with a waveguide coupling the emission and absorption medium with LiFi spectrum operations.

How:

Why:

Flexible circuitry is an inherent part of the next paradigm in custom additive manufacturing of electronics and photonic hardware. In the light of the One Quantum Tablet Per Child, is the need for manufacturing flexible quantum e-paper. Quantum coprocessors add to MCU based computing which provides a high speedup on the edge, the quantum edge for quantum cloud functions, adding an edge for classical cloud functions and a possible hardware random generator for true random numbers, the realistic Z-cloud. This integration of the Q Experience with the normal cloud and the stochastic cloud with edge support leads to easily manufactured e-paper solutions which like Amazon Echo or Google Cloud, are based on true SaaS, with a natural UI through normal written script and even extensible to a role as a graphic tablet.

So What:

Inexpensive e-paper

Story:

When I was in my undergraduate at IIT Madras, I was ridiculed by a well meaning mentor of mine for “crazy thinking”, ideation and innovation on high speed switched optocoupler based transistors, today such technology is extremely useful in HPC and flex-circuit organic design relevant in 3DP, additive custom manufacturing and rapid prototyping.

Applications:

TOF, LIDAR, LiFi, e-paper, Q-Qi

Introduction.

Flexible electronics and display technology is touted as the next innovation in computing, with a direct integration of computing into displays, for applications like smart paper, smart wall paper and a host of (Rost et al. 2004a; Schidleja, Melzer, and von Seggern 2008; Schmechel et al. 2003; Aleshin et al. 2011; Zaumseil 2013; Shigee et al. 2010; Rost et al. 2004b; Rost-Bietsch 2005; Deng et al. 2016; Hotta 2015; Ruden and Smith 2007; Shang et al. 2019; Zhao et al. 2017; Yu et al. 2016; Wei et al. 2008; Ohshima et al. 2009; Moon and Takezoe 2012; Kaushik et al. 2016; Panzer 2007)

Problem Definition.

Fig A: A current mirror design with maximal isolation, for superior design with minimal parasitics.

Given a resistance transfer problem, we design a positive resistor which follows a nonlinear ohm's law, $V=R(I)I$, which at the least can have a small linear window $V=IR$,

The positive resistance is equivalent to a current mirror $I_{\text{Source-Drain}} = I_{\text{gate}} * K$, where K is a constant in a window of operations. K would typically depend on geometry, and the nonlinear conductivity of the light sensitive polymer, inspired by LDR designs. Similar to a relay or opto-coupler, this design provides positive resistance and hence and gain as an amplifier,

switch or other roles. In resistance transfer theory, of digital gating as logic, simple logic devices, with large fan-outs and ideal isolation are possible with this design. In this publication we explore geometric and ideal theoretical properties of such materials without an evaluation of practical material based constraints.

We consider the following MaC based description.

G.OLED, $X(\text{OLED}) = [m, n]$, $L = k(I_{\text{Gate}})$ where k is a constant.

G.LDR, $X(\text{LDR}) = [x, y]$, $R = p(\text{Int}(I(L_i(x, y)))dI$

We derive both a coupling in free space of L and L_i , and dimensions of the LEOFET.

And the relationship between I_{Gate} and $I_{\text{Source-Drain}}$. Given the properties of the polymer, we have a frequency response for switch performance, including the inertia inherent in the design, minimizing capacitive and inductive effects, owing to the small scale of fabrication possible due to the minimalist design. Speculating the possibility of quantum scale computing for easy quantum computers.

We model a photon emission model, for the OLED polymer and the photoelectric effect, including the possibility of trapping light in reflection between the two manifolds and even optical amplification by symmetric designs for single photon computing, useful in TOF and Lidar designs and extremely sensitive photon imaging.

Discussion.

The paper is a minimalist three polymer additive manufacturing solution for LEOFET computing, using waveguide based coupling in light dependent conduction and light emitting polymers, leading to formulations for active resistance, for switching, nonlinear computing and amplification, with highly favorable features

like infinite coupling and isolation principles with very high switching speeds for a large class of polymer materials including graphene based designs.

Future Work.

Practical materials are considered for models and simulations of actual parameter and windows of linear positive resistance design for newer quantum and classical resistance transfer designs.

Several Ising Gate designs with spintronics for high temperature quantum gate models using quantum scale computing, inspired by recent work in graphene atomic transistors also called gfets. Gfets, are a viable candidate for ULSI integration for room temperature scalable Q-GPGPU architectures for number crunching applications. (White, Marini, and Miller 2013; Pasadas and Jimenez 2016; Kurchak, Morozovska, and Strikha 2017)

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